

INCREASING THE PLACE AND ROLE OF PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550190>

Abstract. *In this article, the relationship between the service sector and private entrepreneurship, the analysis of the main economic indicators related to them, and the relevant proposals for increasing the role of private entrepreneurship in the development of the service sector have been developed.*

Keywords: *private business, service industry, self-employment, after-sales service, financial services, trade services, investment projects.*

Introduction

One of the main goals of establishing a socially oriented market economy in Uzbekistan is the priority development of private entrepreneurship. In order to realize this goal, economic reforms are being carried out step by step, and large-scale institutional foundations have been created to increase the role of private entrepreneurship. Legal and regulatory documents guaranteeing the organization of private business activities, free operation, market infrastructure supporting private business have been formed. As a result, to this day, private business entities operate in all aspects of the economy of our country, in the production of machine-building products, in the production of consumer goods, agricultural and food products, and in the provision of services.

In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the goal is to create conditions for the organization of business activities and the formation of permanent sources of income, to increase the share of the private sector in the GDP to 80% and the share of exports to 60%.

The role of private entrepreneurship in the further development of the service sector in our country, especially in the development of information and communication services, repair services for computers, personal items and household goods, services related to intellectual activity, is invaluable. The issue of increasing the role of private entrepreneurship in the service sector is one of the urgent issues.

Literature analysis on the topic

The research conducted by economists L.N.Manitskaya and B.M.Zhukov on the development of the service sector, modernization of service enterprises and organizations is one of the most important scientific achievements in this regard. They developed models of modernization in service enterprises and indicated the external and internal factors affecting it[2].

The issues of achieving economic efficiency in the field of services and finding points of economic growth have been widely studied in the scientific researches of our local scientists Q.J.Mirzaev and M.Q.Pardaev [3]. The issue of development of entrepreneurship in the field of services is reflected in Sh. Kuvondikov's scientific researches [4]. Also, marketing problems in the development of private entrepreneurship [5], organization of sales channels [6], development of

after-sales services [7], issues of customer service in the wholesale trade service [8] were studied in the researches of D.H. Kholmamatov.

Research methodology

The method of analysis and synthesis of statistical data was used to consider the issue of increasing the role of private entrepreneurship in the development of the service sector. Observation methods were also used to study the state of private entrepreneurship in the service sector. In the study, based on monographic observation and logical thinking, personal approaches to the issues of increasing the role of private entrepreneurship in the development of the service sector were put forward.

Analysis and results

Our experience in our country in a short period of time has proven that small business is an important factor of sustainable economic growth. Especially in the conditions of deep structural changes and diversification in the country's economy, private entrepreneurship serves as an important factor in the sustainable development of our national economy, increasing its competitiveness and achieving high macroeconomic indicators.

Reduction of state interference in the economy requires, first of all, continuation of institutional and structural reforms aimed at protecting the right of private property and further strengthening its priority position, encouraging the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

The accumulated experience in the development of private entrepreneurship in our country shows that increasing the level of competitiveness of enterprises requires that they expand and become larger in the course of their activities. However, in some cases, the quantitative limits of enterprises that allow private business entities to have privileges and reliefs established by the state may hinder these processes. During the past period, many enterprises, whose economic potential has increased as a result of the increase in the level of socio-economic development in our country, favorable conditions created for private business entities, in order to continue using these benefits, try to keep the number of employees within the set quantitative limit. This hinders their growth.

Small business and private entrepreneurship are gaining a strong place in the country's economy. In particular, in 2021, 54.9% of GDP, 27.0% of industry, 72.4% of construction, 74.4% of employment, 22.3% of exports and 48.7% of imports will be accounted for by small businesses.

If we pay attention to the analysis of the volume of services provided by the main types of economic activity, the volume of the main services is made up of trade services, transport services and financial services (Table 1). In 2021, a total of 284,165.4 bln. 25.5% of the services provided are for trade services, 23.6% for transport services, and 21.0% for financial services. These types of services make up about 80% of total services.

Table 1

Volume of services by main type of economic activity (billion soums)

Indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Services - total	118 811,0	150 889,8	193 697,8	219 978,5	284 165,4
information and communication	8 196,7	10 332,6	10 891,7	13 852,3	17 755,1

financial activities	15 023,8	21 296,3	34 036,6	45 783,0	59 733,3
transport activities	36 217,2	44 159,4	54 473,5	53 662,9	67 238,6
of which: motor transport	20 232,9	21 786,8	25 527,5	28 474,1	36 249,3
accommodation and food service activities	3 649,6	4 673,3	5 933,6	5 431,7	8 375,4
trade	32 006,9	39 743,4	48 748,2	57 572,7	72 483,3
real estate activities	4 026,5	4 949,2	5 950,7	6 016,9	8 081,1
education	4 402,0	5 416,5	7 164,9	8 539,4	12 021,8
human health activities	1 701,5	2 220,0	3 104,3	3 386,7	5 105,9
renting and leasing	2 589,2	3 297,4	3 733,5	4 149,0	5 351,0
repair of computers and household goods	2 329,2	2 630,7	3 200,1	3 347,8	4 680,5
personal	3 134,4	3 700,6	4 575,6	5 032,2	6 764,1
architectural and engineering activities, technical testing and analysis	1 611,7	2 953,6	4 543,1	4 907,5	6 306,8
other services	3 922,3	5 516,8	7 342,0	8 296,4	10 268,5

Services for repairing computers, personal items and household goods, personal services, services in the field of information and communication are decreasing. It is these services that have the main place in private business, family business, and self-employment. The role of private entrepreneurship is especially important in the development of services in the neighborhoods.

The role and place of small business and private entrepreneurship in the service sector can be seen from the analysis of the main indicators in the economic sectors. 204787.4 billion of trade services in 2021. soums, 144812.7 billion of the remaining services. soums correspond to small business and private entrepreneurship (Table 2).

Table 2

The volume of key indicators of small business and private entrepreneurship in sectors of the economy

Indicators	Unit of measure	Years				
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Industry	billion soums	61367,8	87962,0	83344,2	103020,8	121719,2
Construction	billion soums	22469,4	37451,7	53960,9	63866,6	77762,0
Employment	thousand people	10541,5	10128,8	10318,9	9865,7	10070,7
Export	million US dollars	2759,3	3810,8	4714,8	3100,9	3711,2
Import	million US dollars	7511,9	10916,2	14972,2	10943,3	12389,0
Trade	billion soums	92973,0	114896,4	138920,7	164106,1	204787,4
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	billion soums	152010,5	191759,2	219466,9	253238,2	307280,2
Services	billion soums	69212,7	84433,4	103106,6	114052,7	144812,7
Freight transportation	million tonns	548,8	611,7	641,0	638,9	678,9
Freight turnover	million ton-km	10444,4	11657,7	12152,3	12304,6	13108,1
Passenger transportation	million people	5037,5	5242,6	5345,0	4904,8	5237,6
Passenger turnover	million people km	111435,0	115335,2	117412,7	107766,7	114681,5

The results of our observations show that some types of services are operating in neighborhoods without registration. For example, some types of services that operate without registration in the territory of the neighborhood include a bakery, a bakery or other small catering services, tailoring, shoe repair, hairdressing, small shops (mainly opened from houses), home repair, carpentry, architecture, etc. .

Conclusion

Based on the conclusions reached as a result of the scientific research, the following proposals were developed:

1. In order to increase the role of private entrepreneurship in the development of the service sector, it is first necessary to develop mechanisms for increasing the weight of specific sources of financing for business entities, including public funds, extra-budgetary funds, loans from entrepreneurs, commercial banks and financial institutions, grants from international organizations and foreign countries.

2. Establishment of partnership mechanisms between individual entrepreneurs providing services at home and large and medium-sized enterprises, including the organization of household work, provision of services based on outsourcing contracts. It is especially desirable to organize after-sales service with production enterprises, to attract specialists to service centers.

3. It is necessary to expand the type of services organized along the road and in neighborhoods, to expand the scope of services such as sales services, warehouse services, after-sales service centers, consulting, evaluation.

4. Formation of investment projects for the placement of service facilities in the regions, taking into account the existing demand for services and the capabilities of the regions.

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